

Methodology to develop case-study specific socio-economic scenarios

D3.1: Methodology to develop case-study specific socio-economic scenarios
WP3, T3.2.

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1 Introduction

This Deliverable relates mostly to the activities carried out in Task 3.2. The objective of Task 3.2 is to design a flexible methodology to co-develop socio-economic scenarios. The diversity of case studies calls for a flexible methodology of which some elements are common, but others can be modified to fit case-study characteristics. The purpose of this Deliverable is therefore to provide an overview of the methodology that will be applied in the first series of core case study workshops that aim at developing a set of local socio-economic scenarios. The Deliverable describes the process, approach, and methods used for co-creating socio-economic scenario narratives for the five core case studies.

The Deliverable is structured as follows. Chapter 1 provides an overview of task objectives, background information, and definitions. Chapter 2 presents a brief description of Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), including the existing SSPs relevant to core case studies identified in Task 3.1. Chapter 3 presents the proposed methodology for co-producing the socio-economic scenarios. Chapter 4 provides details on the link between the co-produced SSPs and quantitative model parameter estimates.

1.1 Socio-economic scenarios in DISTENDER

In DISTENDER, the socio-economic scenarios developed in WP3 have a close link with other WPs of the project (Figure 1). On the one hand, the scenarios will provide narratives and (semi-)quantitative input from which model parameters can be derived for models in WP4, WP5, and at a later stage also WP7. On the other hand, the scenarios provide the context that will directly support the co-production of strategies and robust pathways in WP6.

Figure 1. Main lines of scenario development and use in DISTENDER.

Moreover, socio-economic scenario development in DISTENDER will be based on participatory methods and is therefore closely linked to WP2 on co-creation and stakeholder engagement.

The two different ways the socio-economic scenarios are used in DISTENDER call for two different approaches, both of which serve to inform WP6 and help towards the identification of robust pathways to integrated climate change adaptation and mitigation in all core case studies (Figure 1).

The first approach is termed “Story-And-Simulation” (SAS; Alcamo, 2008). This is a ten-step approach in which qualitative socio-economic scenarios are co-produced by stakeholders and subsequently translated to model input. Model outputs of these stakeholder-generated scenarios can then be presented to and discussed with the stakeholders that developed them to increase consistency. In DISTENDER, models that require input from WP3 are being applied in WP4, WP5, and WP7. This approach will be the focus of Chapter 4 in this document.

The second approach is termed “Scenario planning”. This is an approach that links qualitative socio-economic scenarios directly with normative pathways and/or existing policies, actions, and strategies, thereby providing the direct link between socio-economic scenarios and WP6. Strategies and policies are considered “robust” when they can be implemented across a range of plausible futures (the SSPs). The first steps of this approach, notably the development of qualitative socio-economic scenarios, will be the focus of Chapter 3 in this document. The robust strategies themselves will be presented in D6.3.

1.2 Definitions

Below we clarify some of the key words used in DISTENDER WP3, related to socio-economic scenarios. Note that this information is taken directly from the DISTENDER WP3 Glossary, an internal document used to provide information to the case studies.

Scenarios

In the broadest sense, a scenario is future outlook that includes an endpoint description and the milestones leading to that endpoint.

- Scenarios are plausible descriptions of how the future may develop, based on a coherent and internally consistent set of assumptions about key relationships and driving forces. These are often scenarios that include quantitative modelling, and that stress the internal logic of stories to be consistent with models they are linked to.
- Scenarios are credible, challenging, and relevant stories about how the future might unfold that can be told in both words and numbers. These are often scenarios that are developed together with stakeholders in case studies, and that stress the relevance for local end users.

There are two common types of scenarios – both of which are likely to be found within DISTENDER. These are “normative” (or target seeking) and “exploratory” (or “what if”)

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scenarios. Many of the scenarios or projected futures that case studies will be familiar with (e.g., implementation plans towards a strategic target) will be normative scenarios, whilst the SSPs used within WP3 and 6 are exploratory scenarios. The differences between the two is explained below.

Normative scenarios

Normative scenarios have a specific and desirable end point in mind (e.g., the achievement of carbon neutrality) and set out different routes to reach this endpoint. These scenarios are designed to address the question “what **should** happen”. Key elements of normative scenarios are **visions** (a description of the situation in a given year in the future and how the world should look like) and the policies needed to reach this vision. Normative scenarios can therefore be seen as related to policies, spatial plans, and adaptation measures in case studies.

Exploratory scenarios

Exploratory scenarios focus on the question “what **could** happen?”. They are not designed to be predictive and do not consider a particular target or end point. Instead, they are plausible representations of a range of futures, based on the scenario-consistent evolution of drivers. These scenarios intend to explore the breadth of the uncertainty space of future development related to key drivers. There are two important sub-categories that are considered in DISTENDER: climatic scenarios and socio-economic scenarios. Climatic scenarios are being developed in WP4. Socio-economic scenarios set out worlds very different to today, following trajectories that may be quite different to current trends. However, they should follow an internally consistent storyline so as to set out a world that could plausibly take place. No one exploratory scenario is seen to be more/less “likely”, “realistic” or “representative” than another.

Socio-economic scenarios can be defined as plausible representations of futures with respect to key social and economic drivers, such as technological development, economic growth, and migration.

1.3 Starting point for socio-economic scenarios in DISTENDER

In DISTENDER, socio-economic scenario development will be based on a set of (global) existing scenarios, the **Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs)**. These are part of the latest (global) climate change scenarios, which originally included the representative concentration pathways (RCPs; Van Vuuren et al. 2011) and the shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs; O'Neill et al. 2014). Together they are referred to as the RCPxSSP scenarios. The SSPs have been put forward as a set of scenarios that would be a useful starting point for scenarios development at others scales and for other sectors. Contrary to earlier global scenario sets, the SSPs are partly designed to be useful beyond their original purpose of being part of the new global climate scenarios, which makes them particularly suitable for applications to local case studies. Given the focus of DISTENDER on climate mitigation and adaptation, it was decided to use the global and European (see Kok et al., 2019) SSPs as starting point.

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2 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways

In DISTENDER, we will co-develop Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) for the core case studies. This chapter provides an overview of the SSPs and the selection of RCPxSSP combinations in DISTENDER. It further clarifies the original terminology of the RCPs and SSPs and the current phrasing. The chapter ends with presenting the specific starting points for the core case studies, based on the existing SSPs relevant to case studies identified in Task 3.1.

2.1 Scenarios used in DISTENDER

2.1.1 Overview of Shared Socioeconomic Pathways

The SSPs describe plausible alternate changes of societal aspects under different possible futures, such as economic and institutional factors. The SSPs are framed in terms of challenges to climate change mitigation and adaptation (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) representing different challenges to climate change mitigation and adaptation. Figure from O'Neill et al. (2017).

The global SSPs described in O'Neill et al. (2014; 2017) are considered to be “basic SSPs”. They have short and simple storylines, with only enough information to sketch out the different possible futures. These storylines are based on assumptions in changes of societal elements, including demographics, human development, economy and lifestyle, policies and

institutions, technology, and environment and natural resources. For DISTENDER, as for other SSP applications, it is necessary to extend the SSPs and the assumptions so that they are contextualized to the scale and scope of case studies. This includes additional and more detailed information, such as on sectors relevant to the case study.

2.1.2 Combining socio-economic futures and climate forcing

Initially, the new climate scenarios were termed as SSPs and RCPs. The four RCPs were a selection of climate forcing scenarios that were taken from existing literature available at that time. The four RCPs were a representative sample that covered the range of greenhouse gas emission scenarios, including a very high emission scenario (RCP8.5) and a rather low emission scenario (RCP2.6). The newly developed SSPs and existing RCPs were largely independent and could be combined in any way, leading a potential set of 20 (4 RCPs x 5 SSPs) integrated scenarios. Over time, the SSPs were also used to generate emissions scenarios. With the start of the ScenarioMIP (Scenario Model Intercomparison Project) in 2015, the RCPs were gradually phased out and replaced with four SSPs that were used to span the same range of emissions as the RCPs. This has created confusion related to the use of the term SSP, as they now serve a double purpose. Within DISTENDER and for the remainder of this Deliverable, we propose to specify which use the SSPs are serving, discerning the following:

- EM-SSPs. These are global SSPs that are used as input in global Integrated Assessment models to generate greenhouse gas emissions. The EM-SSPs serve as input to global climate models and therefore also climate change. In DISTENDER, the EM-SSPs are used to run climate simulations.
- CCS-SSPs. These are local case study SSPs that are used to understand case-study specific socio-economic changes and inform about robust policy making.

The overall logic of working towards integrated scenarios for all core case studies has not changed, and neither has the logic of combining climate scenarios and socio-economic scenarios. What was originally referred to as 'RCPxSSP combinations' will here be termed 'EM-SSPxCCS-SSP combinations' (short: 'EMxCCS').

2.1.3 Selection procedure of Shared Socioeconomic Pathways

It has been decided to adopt a set of six combinations of EM-SSPs and CCS-SSPs for CCS scenario development (see Table 1). The aim is to co-produce 3-4 scenarios with stakeholders during the first stakeholder workshop. Additional combinations are to open the possibility to vary the climate signal while keeping socio-economic change the same, or vary socio-economic change while keeping climate signal the same. More detail is provided in subsequent sections, the general rationale behind the SSP selection logic is outlined below:

There are a variety of reasons that underlie the decision to select a set of EMxCCS combinations that differ from the set as used by WP4, and which follows the core set of combinations as defined within the ScenarioMIP initiative and thus used by all major Global Circulation Models:

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- EM-SSP selection: The set of four core combinations selected for use in ScenarioMIP includes EM-SSP1 (forcing level as in RCP2.6); EM-SSP2 (RCP4.5); EM-SSP3 (RCP7.0); and EM-SSP5 (RCP8.5). This is also the set that WP4 will use, thus excluding SSP4. This is a good selection, because the EM-SSPs cover the range of uncertainty related to emission levels, similar to the original RCPs. Note that one SSP is linked to one emission level.
- CCS-SSPs selection: It was decided that all five of the CCS-SSPs will be developed within WP3. A subset of those will be developed with stakeholders. Similar to the EM-SSPs, it is important to include those scenarios that are extremes of the uncertainty space covered by the socio-economic scenarios. SSP2 is, by definition, in the middle of the uncertainty space and, therefore, less relevant to develop in the context of their use during the robustness testing. It was therefore decided to exclude CCS-SSP2 from the core set that will be considered to co-produce with stakeholders. Similarly, SSP4 is important as it reflects good levels of mitigation behaviour but highlights the challenges of an unequal society and associated problems.
- Integrated scenarios: Following the logic of combining RCPs and SSPs, four integrated scenarios were then selected by combining the EM-SSPs and the CCS-SSPs. These are: EM2.6xSSP1; EM4.5xSSP4; EM7.0xSSP3; EM8.5xSSP5. In this way, the uncertainty space from both climate change forcing levels and socio-economic change are maximised.
- From discussions with WP5, it became clear that there is the need for some models to be able to test the effect of “climate change only” and “socio-economic change only”. because of which two additional integrated scenarios were included. One additional CCS-SSP1 (combined with a higher climate change forcing); and one additional EM-SSP2 forcing level combined with CCS-SSP2. This led to a set of 6 combinations.
- Depending on the number of participants in a workshop, more or less CCS-SSPs will be co-developed by stakeholders. Given the difficulties that most CCS have to identify stakeholders, this is likely to be less than 4, perhaps in some cases only 2. The minimum number of stakeholders in one scenario development group was set at four.
- SSPs that are not developed by stakeholders will be provided by expert knowledge from WP3, perhaps with help of the CCS partners. The output of WP3 will be a set of 4-6, depending on the wishes from the WP5/7 modellers and WP6 needs.
- Note that there will be a slight mismatch between global assumptions underlying the EM-SSPs and the local CCS-SSPs, both because the set differs, but also because local stakeholders develop a slightly different version of an SSP. This is logical and unavoidable and will only play a very minor role since the impact of CCS-SSPs on global developments can be neglected. Note that these inconsistencies have always been allowed in the design of the RCPxSSP matrix, where underlying socio-economic assumptions of the RCPs do not always match the SSP’s assumptions.

2.1.4 Overview of selected SSPs in DISTENDER

Selection of EM-SSPs: SSPs for global emissions and climate change

Four EM-SSPs have been selected to model climate change (in WP4) following the ScenarioMIP selection:

- SSP126: EM-SSP1 (Global Sustainability) with forcing level 2.6 W/m²
- SSP245: EM-SSP2 (Middle of the Road) with forcing level 4.5 W/m²
- SSP37: EM-SSP3 (Regional inequality) with forcing level 7.0 W/m²
- SSP585: EM-SSP5 (Fossil-fueled development) with forcing level 8.5 W/m²

This covers the range of forcing levels and therefore input for the (global) climate models. SSP4 has not been included as its forcing levels are similar to what is assumed for SSP2.

Selection of CCS-SSPs: SSPs for socio-economic CCS development

All five CCS-SSPs will be developed by WP3. A selection of these will be co-produced by stakeholders; this subset will include SSP4 and exclude SSP2, to maximise input from stakeholders in exploring the extremes of the uncertainty space.

Selection of integrated scenarios: six EM-SSP x CCS-SSP combinations

The general approach of the original RCPxSSP matrix is followed in DISTENDER as well. To the extent possible, there is a coupling between global EM-SSP forcing levels and CCS-SSP socio-economic developments. Yet, the final set of integrated scenarios allows for a decoupling of both types of SSPs, allowing for integration of additional combinations of EM-SSPs and CCS-SSPs. A main advantage of this approach is that it gives a large degree of flexibility at case study level to use different integrated scenarios, e.g., where the global society has high emissions but locally the society is focussing on environmentally friendly behaviour (CCS-SSP1 x EM-SSP8.5), which is locally relevant but globally impossible. A potential disadvantage is that it might increase inconsistencies between (global) climate model assumptions and (regional) scenario and model assumptions. This can be minimised by using the combinations selected by WP4 as much as possible.

Six combinations of SSPs and forcing levels have been selected as broad set to select combinations for each case study (see Table 1). These include the five SSPs and one additional combination including SSP1 (with RCP8.5). This allows not only for the selection of any SSP, but also to vary only the forcing level and not the SSP (for SSP1). In principle, no other combination will be developed by any of the CCS. For all CCS, we aim at the development of 4 SSPs (excluding SSP2). If this is not possible, there is a “minimum set of three SSPs (SSP1,4,5), and an absolute minimum “core set” of two (SSP1, SSP4) that need to be developed.

Table 1. Set of proposed combinations of EM-SSPs and CCS-SSPs for CCS scenario development. In bold is the minimum set of SSPs to be produced by CCS.

Forcing (W/m ²)	CCS-SSP1	CCS-SSP2	CCS-SSP3	CCS-SSP4	CCS-SSP5
2.6	X				
4.5		X		X	

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7.0			X		
8.5	X				X

2.2 Existing Shared Socioeconomic Pathways in DISTENDER case studies

In Task 3.1, we identified existing socio-economic scenarios and relevant information for core case studies. A synthesis of this information is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of identified socio-economic scenarios and most relevant information for core case studies. From Task 3.1 Report.

Case study	Socio-economic scenarios	Scale	Context	Next steps?
Austria (BMK)	AT-Agri-SSPs	National	Agriculture & food systems	Extend national SSPs for sector(s).
	WEM and WAM scenarios	National	Climate mitigation	Determine if relevant input for SSPs.
The North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS)	Dutch-SSPs	National	Health	Extend national SSPs for sector(s) and region.
Dehesas (Spain) and Montados (Portugal) (EURAF)	Iberian-SSPs	Regional	High-end climate change	Extend Iberian SSPs for sector(s).
Guimaraes (PT)	RNC2050 socio-economic scenarios	National	Climate mitigation	Determine how to extend Iberian-SSPs and DISTENDER EURAF SSPs for sector(s).
The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0) (IT)	No long-term socio-economic scenarios until 2050	N/A	N/A	Develop new SSPs, making use of short-term projections.
	Economic projections until 2025	National	GDP, Public Finance, Prices, Employment, Foreign Trade	

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Based on the information collected in Task 3.1, case studies have different starting points for the co-production of socio-economic scenarios. For example, some case studies have existing SSPs that match or are closer to the case study scale than others. This has different implications for what will need to be produced and how existing SSPs will need to be extended (Table 3). In DISTENDER, we will use existing SSPs that are closest to the scale of the case study as the starting point for scenario development.

Table 3. Overview of identified socio-economic scenarios and most relevant information for core case studies. From Task 3.1 Report.

Case study	Existing economic scenarios starting point	socio-scenarios	Scale and case study match	Scope case study match	Next steps?
Austria (BMK)	AT-Agri-SSPs		National – same scale as case study	Agriculture & food systems – different scope to case study	Extend SSPs to case study scope.
The North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS)	Dutch-SSPs		National – different scale to case study (regional)	Health – different scope to case study	Extend SSPs to case study scope and region.
Dehesas (Spain) and Montados (Portugal) (EURAF)	Iberian-SSPs		Regional – provides info about Spain and Portugal at a higher scale	High-end climate change	Extend SSPs to case study scope.
Guimaraes (PT)	Iberian-SSPs and EURAF SSPs		Regional – different scale to case study (local)	High-end climate change	Extend SSPs to case study scope and region. Determine if RNC2050 National Portuguese socio-economic scenarios can be used to support this process.
The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0) (IT)	European SSPs		Continent – different scale to case study (local)	Climate change	Extend SSPs to case study scope and region, making use of short-term projections.

3 Scenario co-production methodology

This chapter presents the proposed methodology for the co-production of socio-economic scenarios in DISTENDER case studies. This chapter first provides an overview of the approach, before presenting the proposed core methods and process. It concludes with a section on case study specific considerations, including logistics.

3.1 Overview of methodological approach

The methodological approach for the development of socio-economic scenarios is based on scenario planning and co-production. This means that qualitative narratives will need to be developed to ultimately support the development of robust strategies in WP6. It also means that the development of socio-economic scenarios will be participatory.

3.1.1 Consistency and flexibility

There are two aspects that are key to consider for the overall methodological approach. First, there is a need for **consistency** across case studies, so that results across case studies can be compared. This means that a set of SSPs and scenario elements (i.e., sectors) need to be core to each case study. At the same time, the diversity of case studies calls for **flexibility** in the methodology, with other elements able to be modified to fit case study characteristics. This means that a balance needs to be struck with comparability through common core elements of the socio-economic scenarios, and flexibility through case study-specific elements.

3.1.2 Core elements of socio-economic scenarios

Each case study will need to co-produce a **minimum set of CCS-SSPs** to allow for comparability across case studies. In DISTENDER, we expect the following CCS-SSPs to be co-produced with stakeholders:

- SSP4 and SSP5 (core set)
- SSP3, SSP4, SSP5 (minimum set)
- SSP1, SSP3, SSP4, SSP 5 (full set)

The sets of SSPs are based on the SSP and forcing level combinations discussed in Section 2.1.2. Also, note that all five CCS-SSPs will be developed by WP3; some without input from stakeholders.

In addition to the minimum set of SSPs, the SSPs themselves will need to include **core elements** that are common to all the case studies. Given the role the scenarios will play in providing model input (see Chapter 4), the major sectors to be modeled in DISTENDER will be included through involving relevant stakeholders from the following sectors: Water, Energy, Health, and Agriculture and Forestry. This will also relate to the phase in the stakeholder workshop on trend indications, which will be common to all case studies.

3.2 Proposed core methods

The core methods for the development of socio-economic scenarios are stakeholder workshops. The general process within which the development of socio-economic scenarios lies is illustrated in Figure 3. Note that steps one and two have already been completed and are reported on in Deliverable 2.1 and Task Report 3.1, respectively. This section therefore focuses on the remaining steps.

Figure 3. Overview of process for developing the socio-economic scenarios in DISTENDER. Stakeholder workshops will be the focus of steps 5-7.

3.2.1 Stakeholder selection

Stakeholders for the co-creation activities on developing socio-economic scenarios will be selected based on the Prospex-CQI method (Gramberger et al., 2015), as outlined in D2.1. We defined the criteria categories based on societal groups that are affected by or affect climate change adaptation and mitigation (the research topic of DISTENDER), the project objective O2, on vulnerable categories inclusion and avoiding the gender gap, and the workshop objective to co-produce a set of socio-economic scenarios for each case study. In particular, it was important to include a range of stakeholder groups in the criteria categories because the workshop objective is about exploring different futures, and different groups have vastly different perspectives on the future (e.g., depending on age group). We therefore defined the following general categories:

Demographic categories include:

- Age (with the aim of including perspectives of youth)
- Gender (with the aim of including perspectives of women and avoiding the gender gap)
- Vulnerable groups (with the aim of including perspectives of racial and ethnic minorities and marginalized groups)

Topical categories include:

- Sectoral affiliation (subcategories include the key sectors for each case study, e.g., energy, agriculture)
- Institutional affiliation (subcategories include government, NGO (including grassroots), business, artists, academia, citizen).

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The resulting stakeholder criteria table with quotas can be found in Table 4. Note that the table provided is a general list of criteria for all case studies, and therefore meant to be adapted to the specific context of each case study through an iterative process. For example, case studies have added additional categories not included in the general list, such as other important sectors relevant for the case. Note that while these tables provide the broad categories to consider for stakeholder selection, the selection and invitation of particular individuals will be carried out by the case studies.

Table 4. Overview of stakeholder criteria and related minimum quota to be invited to the scenario development workshop.

Category	Sector				Institutional affiliation						Demographics			
	Water	Energy	Agriculture	Health	Government	Scientist	NGO* (including grassroots/local NGO)	Artist	Business	Citizen	Age < 30 years	Gender = Women	Vulnerable groups*	
Criteria														
Quota (minimum)	2	2	2	2	All that need to be present in follow-up workshops	2	2	2	2	2	2	At least 1/3 of participants	5	
Stakeholder no. EXAMPLE: SH 1	X						X					X	X	X

3.2.2 Preparation for stakeholder workshops

To increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the stakeholder workshops, preparation activities will be offered for support. This includes pre-workshop analysis and supportive webinars.

Pre-workshop analysis

To support the development of socio-economic scenarios in the stakeholder workshops, analyses will be carried out before the workshops based on a survey sent to case study stakeholders. This will focus on main factors to be included in the scenarios that are relevant for the case study. This list of main factors can include social, economic, technological, environmental, and political drivers that are relevant to the case study. The resulting analyses will be discussed in a plenary during the workshop. Another area that is included in the pre-workshop survey relates to existing strategies of climate change adaptation and mitigation, in relation to task 6.2 and the final activity in the workshop.

Supportive webinars

Two supportive webinars will be organized to prepare case studies for the stakeholder workshops. The objective of one supportive webinar would be to prepare case studies on workshop content, specifically on the SSPs. The objective of the other supportive webinar would be to prepare case studies on the process of the workshop, including facilitation skills and stakeholder engagement. Both webinars will include presentations of their respective topics and provide an opportunity for case studies to ask questions. The maximum time for the webinars will be two hours.

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3.2.3 Developing socio-economic scenarios

The primary aim of the first set of stakeholder workshops is to co-produce a set of socio-economic scenarios between now (2023) and 2050 for the respective case studies, based on the SSPs. These scenarios explore how socio-economic, political, institutional, organizational, and cultural factors will change under different possible futures, thereby ultimately supporting the development of integrated climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies. In addition, the first set of workshops will also seek to provide trend indications for a selected set of model input variables and discuss climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies in the context of the developed socio-economic scenarios.

The co-production of socio-economic scenarios will build on existing socio-economic scenarios relevant to the case studies. The starting point will differ per case study. Some case studies have existing socio-economic scenarios in the form of national- or regional-level SSPs, that differ in the scope and/or scale that is needed. The starting point for these case studies will therefore be the national- or regional-level SSPs. Other case studies may have no existing national or regional level SSPs or other socio-economic scenarios. The starting point for these case studies will therefore be European-level SSPs (Kok et al., 2019) (ref). In both cases, the aim of the stakeholder workshop will be to contextualize the existing socio-economic scenarios to the case studies (with respect to scale and sector(s) where relevant) and revise narratives accordingly.

Process of stakeholder workshop

Although the starting point may differ per case study, the overall process, and main phases of the first stakeholder workshop remains the same. This is outlined in Figure 4, and in further detail below.

Figure 4. The process and main phases of the stakeholder workshop on developing qualitative narratives for socio-economic scenarios.

1. Setting the scene

This includes icebreakers and participant introductions, as well a brief overview of objectives and expectations. There will also be a short presentation of DISTENDER and the process and content of the existing global and European SSPs.

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2. Plenary discussion on main drivers

This will be based on pre-workshop analysis of a survey, to start with a short list of important factors relevant to the case study that can be discussed. These factors are meant to serve as building blocks for scenario development.

3. BOG1: developing the case study SSP narratives

Break-out groups (BOGs) should have a minimum of 4-5 participants to ensure broad expertise. Every BOG will develop 1 SSP. The total number of SSPs depends on the total number of participants. For 4 SSPs, about 20-25 participants are needed.

3a. Reading one-pagers. One-page summaries of the higher-level SSPs are provided during the workshop that give a short narrative and a table with trend indications for main factors. Participants are to familiarise themselves with the SSP.

3b. Discussion on changes for main factors (from Step 2) in SSP

3c. Identification of main events and developments between 2023 and 2050. Participants will put these on a timeline. Participants will develop newspaper headings based on this. They will describe the end situation in 2050 in some more detail.

3d. Developing the narrative. Participants will be provided with guiding questions to develop the qualitative narratives for their SSP, such as: How are events connected? What are main drivers behind change? How do you depart from the current situation?

3e. Creating the scenario title.

4. Presentation of SSPs

Presentation of all CCS-SSPs that were developed during the workshop and plenary discussion. The aim is to have all stakeholders involved in all scenarios that are co-produced.

5. BOG2: Trend indications and land use change

Participants will provide a trend indication for selected set of model input variables (-5 to +5 for changes between 2023 and 2050). The set of variables will be selected with WP4, WP5, WP7, and may include variables such as: land use change classes (urban, agriculture, forest), population, GDP, other economic indicators.

6. BOG3: Current climate policies

Participants will discuss existing policies related to climate change mitigation and adaptation in the core sectors of the case study. They will build on the inventory of current efforts made earlier in the project (Task 6.2) and the pre-workshop survey. The focus is to discuss some of the existing policies in the context of the previously developed socio-economic scenarios, to build understanding on the link between scenarios and robust strategies.

Additional co-production techniques for stakeholder workshop

The basis of the stakeholder workshop will be co-production techniques suitable for explorative and creative thinking. Given the rather short duration of most workshops, the fact that some of them will be online events, and the varying degree of expertise of co-facilitators, rather straightforward techniques will be used in most of the workshops, based on brainstorming using sticky notes. However, additional techniques are available that might be employed in some of the workshops. Table 5 provides an overview of some of such co-production techniques that could be used. This list includes examples of co-production techniques that are used in participatory scenario development, but it is not exhaustive. Co-

production technique descriptions are based on the [SENSES co-production techniques toolkit](#) (Senses, 2020).

Table 5. Co-production techniques that can be used in stakeholder workshops to develop qualitative narratives of socio-economic scenarios

Technique	Description	Use in workshop
Brainstorming	This interactive technique is used to promote creative thinking to develop ideas around a specific topic, for example through the use of sticky notes.	Brainstorming can be done using sticky notes, to generate ideas related to scenario development, such as key drivers of future socio-economic change and future trends under different futures.
Futures Wheel	This technique allows for targeted brainstorming about the future. A trend/event is written in the middle, with two or more “rings” around it. Primary impacts are written in the first ring, secondary impacts in the second, etc.	The Futures Wheel can be used to explore implications of changes in key socio-economic trends, for narrative development.
Science Fictioning	In this technique, participants imagine fictional narratives and images of developments in the future. Participants then discuss the drivers, impacts, and implications of these developments.	Science Fictioning can be used for developing the storylines of the socio-economic scenarios.
Role playing	Role playing is a gaming and simulation technique in which participants act out fictional character roles within a narrative.	This technique can allow participants to gain an understanding of the key elements of future worlds and the responses of different actors.
Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping	Fuzzy Cognitive Maps represent mental models of participants regarding a (complex) system, including semi-quantitative causal relationships between concepts.	Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping can be integrated in the process of co-producing scenario narratives by providing semi-quantitative insights on system dynamics and how they may change under different futures (Kok, 2009).
Wildcards	Wildcards are low-probability, high-impact events that occur suddenly and act as a shock to the system.	In scenario development, wildcards can be used to develop scenarios with wildcards as a starting point or with wildcards used to extend the existing scenario narrative.

3.2.4 Trend indications

The second aim of the stakeholder workshop and of BOG2 is for participants to provide trend indications for a selected set of model input variables. These are relative trend indications that range from -5 to +5 for changes between 2023 and 2050. The set of model input variables to be discussed in the workshop will be selected in collaboration with WP4, WP5, and WP7. In addition, elements that are useful for WP6 were also discussed and added. An example of a trend indications table that would be the output of a stakeholder workshop is provided in Table 6.

Table 6. An example of trend indications of key variables, including model input parameters. Increases or decreases compared to 2023 are indicated for three time periods (2023-2030; 2030-2040; 2040-2050). Note that trend indications in this table are fictional and meant only as an example of the expected output.

Variable	SSP1	SSP3	SSP4	SSP5
Population growth	0, 0, 0	+++ , ++, +	+ , +, 0	+ , +, +
GDP	+, ++, +++	-, --, ---	0, 0, -	+++ , +, 0
Social capital	+, ++, +++	+, 0, 0	--, ---, ---	+, 0, -

Process of BOG2:

Groups with the same composition as during BOG1, where they developed one SSP, now build on the results from BOG1 and for “their own” SSP, complete a table with model parameters and other scenario characteristics. The two main questions to be answered are:

1. What is the trend until 2050 for the parameter? (trend from -5 to +5)
2. What is the logic behind the change in the SSP? (2-3 sentences that explain why the change is as indicated. The final set of model variables and other scenario elements that will be used in all stakeholder workshops is given in Table 7.

Table 7. List of model parameters and other scenario elements to be discussed during stakeholder workshop.

Element	What
Total population	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
GDP growth	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Environmental behaviour	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Water ¹	Prioritise list of water sectors. In case of water stress, which sector will be prioritised?
Energy ³	Prioritise list of energy sources. What is main source of energy?
Food ²	Prioritise farming practices. Conventional or organic?
Agricultural area	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5

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Social capital	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Manufactured capital	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Human capital	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5

1: agriculture, domestic, industry, and nature

2: organic, conventional

3: Select main source of energy (electricity, natural gas, fossil fuels) for five sectors: industry, residential, commercial, agricultural and transportation.

Detailed explanation of model parameters and scenario elements

Total population: Ask stakeholders for the trend in total population on a scale from +5 to -5 in a given time period.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP):

This is a measure for economic development. Ask stakeholders for the trend in yearly average GDP growth in a given time period.

Environmental behaviour:

This is an index for overall environmental behaviour. An increase, in general, relates to an increase in pro-nature attitude for any type of actor. This could relate to development of green technology; dietary preferences towards vegetarianism; direct nature protection measures; mobility; heating systems etc. It depends on the scenario that was developed, what actor group(s) should be specified (e.g., NGOs, citizens, policy makers, businesses) and what the increase/decrease refers to specifically. The accompanying text should explain this.

Water:

Given a certain water supply, what will be the order of priority when choices have to be made for satisfying water demand. In which order will the water demand be satisfied? For a given time period, four sectors should be ordered from first priority (1) to last priority (4). The four sectors are: agriculture, domestic, industry, and nature.

Agriculture:

This aspect relates to food production. Will organic food production be prioritised, or conventional farming systems? For a given time period, two production systems should be ordered as first (1) or second (2) priority.

Energy:

This aspect relates to energy consumption. Which type of energy will be prioritised in the main energy using sectors (industry, residential, commercial, agricultural and transportation)? For a given time period, provide the most important source of energy for each of the five sectors. Included are three types of energy: electricity, natural gas, fossil fuels; and five sectors: industry, residential, commercial, agricultural and transportation.

Agricultural area:

This aspect relates to the change in total area used for production of agricultural products. This includes arable land (crops) and grassland (for grazing). A main element to consider

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here is the choice to either produce all food locally or to focus on food import. Important to invite stakeholders to include this in their description.

Detailed explanation of 'capitals'

We are also interested in quantifying the stocks of resources that people have available to adapt and cope with the challenges of climate change within the scenarios in addition to financial resources. These include stocks of human, social and manufactured capital detailed below. For the same climate impact, people with lower levels of each of these capitals are more likely to be more vulnerable than those with higher levels of capital. All three are more general indices, that are defined as:

Social capital: index covering all aspects that relate to structures, institutions, networks, and relationships. It includes families, communities, businesses, voluntary organisations, and the political system.

Manufactured capital: index covering all aspects that relate to the entire physical man-made stock, including infrastructure (roads, canals), buildings, but also machinery, cars, etc.

Human capital: index covering all aspects that relate to the individual knowledge, skills, and health that people invest in and accumulate. It includes education, training, intelligence, skills, health, etc., but also often assumes physical entities such as hospital, health care system, universities etc.

For all three, changes could relate to many different aspects of the scenario. an indication of the overall trend should be provided; the accompanying text should explain what the decrease/increase specifically refers to, using the examples provided in the descriptions above.

3.2.5 Climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies

The third aim of the stakeholder workshop is a discussion on the main strategies related to climate change mitigation and adaptation in the core sectors of the case study. This will build on the inventory of current policies carried out in Task 6.2, as well as the pre-workshop survey provided to participants. This part of the workshop will be conducted to ultimately serve the development of robust strategies (Task 6.3). It will therefore focus on a discussion of the existing strategies in the context of the previously developed socio-economic scenarios.

3.2.6 Follow-up after the workshop

Following the workshop, the results will be presented to the stakeholders. This will be done through a written document with the direct results from the workshop, and stakeholders will be invited to provide comments. Stakeholders will also be asked to fill in a questionnaire, also related to the purposes of other work packages (e.g., evaluation). A report with the analysis and further processing of the resulting CCS-SSPs will be produced and used to provide input for other WPs.

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3.3 Case study specific considerations

Although the overall methodology is generally the same for case studies, there are specific considerations that need to be taken into account when designing the workshops that differ per case study. For example, case studies that are smaller may more easily be able to have a live format for the workshop than case studies with a larger size (e.g., national level). Moreover, different additional sectors are of interest to different case studies. These considerations are outlined in Table 8, for the core case studies of DISTENDER.

Table 8. Case study-specific workshop considerations.

Case study	Scenario workshop	Format	Sectors
	Workshop: From scratch or adapting existing SSP	Live/online	Any additional specific sectors to include in scenarios?
Austria (BMK)	Adapt existing national SSPs to case study context	Live	Transport
The North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS)	Adapt existing national SSPs to case study context	Live	Coastal areas
Dehesas (Spain) and Montados (Portugal) (EURAF)	Adapt existing regional SSPs to case study context	Online	Agroforestry
Guimaraes (PT)	Adapt existing regional SSPs and national socio-economic scenarios to case study context	Online	Heritage Forestry Biodiversity
The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0) (IT)	Develop new SSPs from scratch	Online	Biodiversity Forestry Economic Tourism Food

Similarly, while many of the logistical considerations for the stakeholder workshops will be the same across case studies, there will be some differences depending on the format of the workshop (Table 9).

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Table 9. Logistical considerations for the first stakeholder workshop depending on format.

	Live	Online
Number of workshops	1	1
Workshop duration	1 full day	2 half-days (3 hours each)
Number of invited participants	20-25	20-25
Number of facilitators	1 main facilitator and 3-4 co-facilitators (depending on number of break out groups and participants)	1 main facilitator and 3-4 co-facilitators (depending on number of break out groups and participants)

3.3.1 Preliminary workshop agenda

Preliminary workshop agendas have been drafted for both the live and online format of the workshop. Note that the times given are examples and will be adapted to the appropriate start and end time for each case study.

Agenda: live workshop 1

About 6-8 hours workshop + 30 min time before workshop for registration and coffee.

Time (example)	Duration	Agenda item
8:30-9:00	30 min	Registration and coffee
9:00-9:15	15 min	Welcome and overall introduction (host, DISTENDER, program, and rules)
9:15-9:20	5 min	Who is who (introduction of non-stakeholders and workshop roles)
9:20-9:50	30 min	Participant introductions (introduce your neighbour)
9:50-10:05	15 min	Introducing the SSPs
10:05-10:15	10 min	Coffee & tea break
10:15-10:45	30 min	Plenary on main factors
10:45-10:55	10 min	Group divisions & participants walk to BOG areas
10:55-12:25	1.5 hr	BOG1: developing the SSP narratives
12:25-13:25	1 hr	Lunch
13:25-14:25	1 hr	Plenary: presentations on SSPs (15 min/group, including discussion)
14:25-15:15	50 min	BOG2: trend indications and land use change
15:15-15:25	10 min	Coffee & tea break
15:25-16:15	50 min	BOG3: current climate change strategies
16:15-16:30	15 min	Next steps and closing statements

Agenda: online workshop 1

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Day 1 – 3 hours

Morning (example)	Afternoon (example)	Duration	Agenda item
8:45-9:00	12:45-13:00	15 min	Open virtual room, check registration
9:00-9:15	13:00-13:15	15 min	Welcome and overall introduction
9:15-9:20	13:15-13:20	5 min	Who is who
9:20-9:40	13:20-13:40	20 min	Participant introductions (plenary)
9:40-9:55	13:40-13:55	15 min	Introducing the SSPs
9:55-10:25	13:55-14:25	30 min	Plenary on main factors (building blocks for scenarios, based on survey)
10:25-10:30	14:25-14:30	5 min	Group divisions
10:30-10:35	14:30-14:35	5 min	Break or energizer
10:35-11:55	14:35-15:55	1 hr 20 min	BOG1: developing the SSP narratives
11:55-12:00	15:55-16:00	5 min	Wrap-up (invite them to come tomorrow again, emphasize continual process)

Day 2 – 3 hours

Morning	Afternoon	Duration	Agenda item
8:45-9:00	12:45-13:00	15 min	Open virtual room, check registration
9:00-10:00	13:00-14:00	1hr	Plenary: presentations on SSPs (15 min/group, including discussion)
10:00-10:50	14:00-14:50	50 min	BOG2: trend indications and land use change
10:50-10:55	14:50-14:55	5 min	Break or energizer
10:55-11:45	14:55-15:45	50 min	BOG3: current climate change strategies
11:45-12:00	15:45-16:00	15 min	Next steps and closing statements

4 Scenario quantification methodology and models

The final output of Task 3.3 is a full set of five CCS-SSPs for all the five core case studies. These scenarios will consist of narratives; tables with trend indications; land use change modelling results; and a small selection of quantitative estimates of key model parameters. As with the trend indications, this will be discussed with WP4, WP5, and WP7. It is likely that most of this work will happen without the input of stakeholders, and it will therefore not be part of the co-production methodology. A short overview of the approach and concrete methods is included here to provide a full overview of how the various SSP-related products will be produced. For more details, we refer to the Deliverables from WP4 and WP5.

4.1 Land use modelling with the iCLUE model

The iCLUE model (Verweij et al., 2018) will be used to produce spatially explicit land use change maps. The iCLUE model has two main components where first overall land use changes (in hectares) are projected. These total changes are then spatially explicitly allocated. Model input for overall changes will be partly based on stakeholder-generated estimates of trends in major land use classes, and partly on project partners from WP3 and WP5.

The main method of producing land use change scenarios is through the combined use of the iCLUE model and a European-level Integrated Assessment Platform. The IAP produces outputs for entire EU-27+ for each SSP-RCP combination. The iCLUE model uses that output as input and translates the IAP land use classes to a selection of CORINE classes. The iCLUE model will be run at national scale for five countries (Spain, Portugal, Italy, Austria, the Netherlands). Most data are available at 250x250 meter spatial resolution. Runs could potentially be provided for 100x100 meter resolution.

4.1.1 Input from stakeholder workshop

The list of scenario elements to be given trend indications by stakeholders includes an estimate of changes in total agricultural area. The narratives of most CCS-SSPs are expected to cover urban area and perhaps natural vegetation or forest cover. Information on some of the main land use classes will thus be taken directly from the co-produced SSPs and combined with the output of the IAP.

4.1.2 Additional model parameterisation – the CORINE land cover map

The CORINE land cover map will be used as the starting point for the iCLUE model. The CORINE land cover map consists of 44 classes in a 3-level hierarchical classification system. In the tables below, an overview is given of the classes that WP3 could provide dynamic future estimates for by SSP (Table 10) and a preliminary matching between the CORINE classes and the output indicators of the IMPRESSIONS IAP (Table 11).

Note that a (large) number of CORINE classes are excluded from this table, because they relate to natural vegetation dynamics. Changes, e.g., from coniferous to deciduous forest cannot be linked to socio-economic changes and falls beyond the capacity of iCLUE and of WP3. Details will be discussed with the WP modellers after the stakeholder workshops have been completed.

Table 10. Classes from the CORINE land cover map that can be linked to socio-economic scenarios.

Class to be considered dynamically	Name	Comments
1	Urban	Includes all artificial structure associated with urban
211	Non-irrigated arable land	
212	Permanently irrigated land	Could also relate to illegal irrigation
22	Cultivated trees, forest plantations	Large diversity of crops
231	Pastures	Only within agricultural areas
241	Annual crops with permanent crops	Mix of 21 and 22
242	Complex cultivation patterns	Mix of 21 and 22 and 23
243	Land principally occupied by agriculture	Could be the same as 21
244	Agro-forestry areas	Mix of all, with special attention in some core case studies
31	Forest (broad leaved and coniferous)	No subdivision into type of forest
32	Natural grasslands, shrubs, woodlands	No subdivision into type of natural non-forest vegetation

Table 11. Linking CORINE and the IAP.

CORINE class	CORINE Name	IAP indicator
1	Urban	Urban%
211	Non-irrigated arable land	IntensiveArable%; Arable%
212	Permanently irrigated land	IntensiveArable%; Arable%; Irrigused Mm3
22	Cultivated trees, forest plantations	mgd_Forest%
231	Pastures	IntensiveGrass%
241	Annual crops with permanent crops	IntensiveArable%; Arable%
242	Complex cultivation patterns	IntensiveArable%; Arable%
243	Land principally occupied by agriculture	IntensiveArable%; Arable%
244	Agro-forestry areas	IntensiveArable%; Arable% + mgd_Forest%
31	Forest (broad leaved and coniferous)	unmgd_Forest%
32	Natural grasslands, shrubs, woodlands	ExtensiveGrass%; VExtensiveGrass%

4.1.3 Model output

For every CCS and for the full set of CCS-SSPs, yearly spatially explicit land use change maps will be produced with a spatial resolution of at least 250x250 m. The exact land use classes that will be covered will be discussed with WP5 modellers.

4.2 Climate change impact models

A variety of climate change impact models will be applied that need parameterisation of a large number of model parameters that are related to socio-economic changes. Only a very small part of those can be estimated using the output from the first series of stakeholder workshops. Changes in an additional set of important model parameters will be provided by WP3 experts, based on the CCS-SSPs and other data, such as input from the IAP. The remainder of the model parameters will be estimated directly by modellers. Below is some more detail on these three options.

4.2.1 Options for model parameter estimation

1. Stakeholder generated

Information comes from core case study stakeholders, either external or internal. Most of this information will not be quantitative, but in the form of trend indications (from -5 to +5) or narratives from the SSPs. Trend indications can then be used by the modellers to translate to quantitative changes. Three sub-options have been identified:

- 1a. External stakeholders: narratives or trend indications for “easy” variables. Changes in model variables that can easily be understood by a broad range of non-model expert stakeholders can be determined by them. Examples include “population growth”, “GDP”, or “percentage of food imported”. See Section 3.2.4 for more details on what was included in the stakeholder workshops.
- 1b. Internal stakeholders: trend indications. Internal stakeholders could be asked more than once to assess changes in a range of parameters. Also here, focus should be on model variables that can easily be understood by stakeholders. Because internal stakeholders are also project partners within DISTENDER, multiple interaction moments are possible which allows for iteration between quantitative numbers and trends.
- 1c. Experts, modellers, and/or internal stakeholders. The aim can also be to directly quantify model variables. Quantification can happen during meetings where a mix of DISTENDER project partners, modellers, and/or internal stakeholders come together. This would allow for direct iteration between modellers with model expertise and stakeholders with scenario expertise.

2. Input from other models

Information is provided by other models, either those used within DISTENDER, or those that are not but that have compatible data.

2a. Other models within DISTENDER. For a selection of variables (related to WP5 climate change impact models), changes will be provided by the output of other models. If decided, parameterization will not involve WP3, but can be an internal modelling decision.

2b. Other models outside of DISTENDER. IAP, GLOBIOM, IMAGE, etc. Particularly for land cover change, there are number of other models available that have produced spatially explicit land cover change maps for a selection of SSPs and a range of land use/cover classes.

3. Direct estimation by modellers

For detailed, specific variables, the expertise of the modellers (again, particularly in WP5) themselves needs to be relied on. This refers to specific model settings that have a weak link to socio-economic changes as described in the SSPs and that can be independently parameterized. A check by WP3 on final estimates is needed, but initiative is with the modellers.

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5 Conclusions and further steps

In DISTENDER, we will co-produce a set of socio-economic scenarios with each core case study. The proposed core methods for this are stakeholder workshops. The first series of stakeholder workshops will have three separate aims. The first and primary aim is the development of qualitative narratives for the socio-economic scenarios, building on the existing SSPs. The minimum set of SSPs to be co-produced is three (SSP1, SSP4, and SSP5). The second aim is for stakeholders to provide trend indications for a selected set of model input variables. The third aim is for stakeholders to discuss the main strategies related to climate change adaptation and mitigation in the core sectors of the case study. This aim is meant to link with the work of WP6, by providing stakeholders the opportunity to learn about the link between socio-economic scenarios and robust strategies. In this deliverable, we have proposed a design of the process and main phases of the stakeholder workshops to achieve these aims, complemented by a short introduction of the modelling process that will follow after qualitative scenarios are completed.

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6 References

- Alcamo, J. (2008). Environmental futures: the practice of environmental scenario analysis. *Developments in Integrated Environmental Assessment - Volume 2*. Elsevier, Amsterdam
- Gramberger, M., Zellmer, K., Kok, K., & Metzger, M. J. (2015). Stakeholder integrated research (STIR): A new approach tested in climate change adaptation research. *Climatic Change*, 128(3), 201–214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-014-1225-x>
- Jäger, J., Rounsevell, M., Harrison, P.A., Omann, I., Dunford, R., Kammerlander, M., Pataki, G. (2014). Assessing policy robustness of climate change adaptation measures across sectors and scenarios. *Climatic Change*. 128. 10.1007/s10584-014-1240-y.
- Kok, K. (2009). The potential of Fuzzy Cognitive Maps for semi-quantitative scenario development, with an example from Brazil. *Global Environmental Change*, 19(1), 122–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2008.08.003>
- Kok, K., Pedde, S., Gramberger, M., Harrison, P.A., Holman, I. (2019). New European socio-economic scenarios for climate change research: operationalising concepts to extend the shared socio-economic pathways. *Regional Environmental Change* 19: 643-654. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-018-1400-0>
- O'Neill, B. C., Kriegler, E., Ebi, K. L., Kemp-Benedict, E., Riahi, K., Rothman, D. S., van Ruijven, B. J., van Vuuren, D. P., Birkmann, J., Kok, K., Levy, M., & Solecki, W. (2017). The roads ahead: Narratives for shared socioeconomic pathways describing world futures in the 21st century. *Global Environmental Change*, 42, 169–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.01.004>
- O'Neill, B. C., Kriegler, E., Riahi, K., Ebi, K. L., Hallegatte, S., Carter, T. R., Mathur, R., & van Vuuren, D. P. (2014). A new scenario framework for climate change research: The concept

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of shared socioeconomic pathways. *Climatic Change*, 122(3), 387–400.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-0905-2>

SENSES. (2020). *Methods and tools for scenario co-production* [The Senses Toolkit]. Methods

and Tools for Scenario Co-production. <https://climatescenarios.org/finder/techniques/>

Van Vuuren, D.P., Edmonds, J., Kainuma, M., Riahi, K., Thomson, A., Hibbard, K., Hurtt, G.C.,

Kram, T., Krey, V., Lamarque, J.-F. (2011). The representative concentration pathways: an

overview. *Climatic Change* 109:5–31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-011-0148-z>

Verweij, P., Cormont, A., van Eupen, M., Kok, K., te Roller, J., Pérez-Soba, M., Janssen, S.,

Staritsky, I. (2018). Improving the applicability and transparency of land use change

modelling: The iCLUE model. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 108: 91-90.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.07.010>

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Annexes

Annex 1. Template for process document

Process document to prepare for the first stakeholder workshop (online): socio-economic scenarios

Basic information:

Date of workshop:

Location:

Number of participants: [number] (external stakeholders); [number] (internal and project members);

How are participants traveling to the workshop?

Confirmed:

X DISTENDER team members (names)

X CCS staff (names)cc

X External stakeholders

X breakout groups

Booked for X participants

Personnel preparations needed

X needs to arrange travel to workshop location. → who books travel and who books hotel?

Plenary: 1 facilitator, 1 notetaker, 1 observer (if available)

For every BOG: 1 facilitator, 1 notetaker (if available; could be any project person, or any student)

For logistics: 1 main contact point for all stakeholder questions; 1 executor for logistics such as coffee, lunch, badges, etc.

Overall: 5 facilitators, 5 notetakers, 1 observer, 1 main contact for SHs, 1 logistics person

This can become less, when there are less BOGs, or when BOGs don't have a notetaker.

Role	Name(s)	Comments
Main facilitator		
Co-facilitators (BOGs)		Need to receive a training. Webinar planned on DATE.
Note taker (plenary and BOGs)		For live workshops, this role can be combined with visual production use during BOG 1.
Observer		
SSP expert		Can be combined with another role.
Logistics person		
Contact person for SHs		

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Workshop preparations (needed before start of workshop)List of factors to include in the socio-economic scenarios based on pre-workshop survey

We decided to select a list of factors before the start of the workshop to shorten the time total program, by making use of a pre-workshop survey sent to stakeholders when they agree to participate. A list of 5-7 factors is needed, 5 being an absolute minimum. The factors need to cover a broad set of direct and indirect drivers that influence the socio-economic scenarios.

Training webinars

Two training webinars need to be held (for all CCS together):

- Webinar on content (SSPs) – 16th May
- Webinar on process and facilitation – 17th May

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Workshop program, material and responsible persons**Day 1 - 3 hours**

Duration	Agenda item	Material needed	Person responsible	Comments
30 min	Final check of technical situation.	-		A pre-workshop check is essential. Could also happen on previous day
15 min before workshop starts	Open virtual room Check registration	List of individuals & informed consent form status.	Welcome people – X Check registration (informed consent forms) – X	
15 minutes	Welcome and overall introduction 1. Introduction from host (3 min) 2. Introduction DISTENDER (7 min) 3. Introduction on day's program & rules and invitations (e.g. Chatham rules, are you okay with note-taking, taking photos (screenshots), recording? Note that we will anonymize after etc.) (3 min)	Presentation slides.	1. Developing presentation – X Presenting – X 2. Developing presentation – X Presenting – X 3. Developing presentation – X Presenting – X	1. Need for a short welcoming word either from host of location or project representative (3 min) 2. Need short introduction about DISTENDER (3 min) 3. Need a short overview of the agenda for today (3 min) The person that opens is the main facilitator.
5 min	Who is who? Quick introduction of the non-stakeholders (facilitators, project team, observers, etc.)		X makes introductions for everyone	
20 minutes	Participant introductions Participants introduce themselves in a round based on basic questions and warm up question. (1 min maximum/participant).	Introduction questions.	Preparing questions – X.	
15 minutes	Introducing the SSPs Presentation on SSPs, including: - Summary of global SSPs	Presentation slides.	Developing presentation script and slides – X	Draft presentation sent to X by DATE? Final presentation sent to X for translation by DATE?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Summary of European SSPs - Summary of regional/national SSPs when relevant - Space for questions 		Presenting - X Facilitating discussion - X	Highlight: a) Credibility - 2000 peer reviewed papers, policy makers have used them, etc.; b) Link to robustness - can think about reminder of how the SSPs will link to the strategies.
5 minutes	Break (or energizer)	TBD	Prepare and lead energizer - X	
30 minutes	<p>Plenary on main factors</p> <p>1. Presentation on factors based on survey responses (10 min)</p> <p>2. Discussion: what are current and future drivers of change? Building blocks for scenarios. (20 min)</p> <p>Make clear to stakeholders: this will be used as a tool for facilitators of BOGs and as building blocks for the stakeholders to build the scenarios, but key to note that stakeholders can discuss different factors too (they do not need to limit themselves to the list, there to be used for inspiration).</p>	Presentation slides.	<p>1. Analysis of survey (Jay, Karsten, Viktoria? TBD.).</p> <p>Developing presentation script and slides- X.</p> <p>Translation of script and slides? – X.</p> <p>Presenting – X</p> <p>2. Facilitating discussion – X</p> <p>Observer – X</p> <p>Notetaker - X.</p> <p>Revise printed list of factors based on discussion – X.</p>	<p>Draft presentation sent to X by DATE? Final presentation sent to X for translation by DATE?</p> <p>Plenary session for all stakeholders to agree on list of factors to use. Preliminary list should be adapted according to this discussion.</p>
5 min	<p>Group divisions & go to BOGs</p> <p>4 groups if possible.</p> <p>If 15 or less: 3 scenarios (SSPs: ...)</p> <p>If 10 or less: 2 scenarios (SSPs: ...)</p>	Proposed division on slides.	<p>Prepare proposal for group division – X.</p> <p>Facilitate – X</p>	

1 hr 20 min	<p>BOG1: SSP narratives Group discussion on scenario in 4 groups with group facilitator.</p> <p>1. Introduction to scenario and activity. (5 min) 2. Participants read 1 page scenario description. (5 min) 3. Questions/clarifications-main thing here is to make sure that participants are HAPPY working on this scenario. (5 min) 4. Creative development of scenarios. (75 min). 4a. Agree on 2050 situation of case study area in SSP world. 4b. Identify main developments and events between 2023 and 2050. Put those on timeline. Add newspaper headings. 4c. Develop foundation for the narrative. How are the events and developments connected? 4d. Add title.</p>	2. 1-pager SSP EU/Global 4. Virtual board prepared.	<p>Co-facilitators: SSP1- X SSP3- X SSP4- X SSP5- X</p> <p>Note-takers (could be any project person, or any student): SSP1- X SSP3- X SSP4- X SSP5- X</p> <p>Main facilitator and move between groups to keep all on track - X</p> <p>Prepare one-pagers- X</p> <p>Prepare Miro board – X</p>	Key important thing for facilitators, is that the specific SSP is NOT about the likelihood that it will happen, it is about what would you do IF it happens, it's about keeping eye on the prize (strategies), BUT also SH need to feel that the scenario they are working on are credible.
5 min	<p>Wrap-up for the day Invite stakeholders to come again tomorrow, emphasize that this is a continual process.</p>	-	Present - X	

Day 2- 3 hours

15 min before workshop starts	<p>Open virtual room Check registration</p>	List of individuals & informed consent form status.	Welcome people – X Check registration (informed consent forms) – X	
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1 hour	<p>Plenary: presentations on SSPs</p> <p>Groups present results. 15 minutes/group (assuming 4 groups). ~5 minutes presentation + 10 minutes questions, comments, discussion.</p> <p>Aim is to have all stakeholders involved in all scenarios.</p>		<p>Participants lead!</p> <p>Facilitator (only if needed) – X</p> <p>Observer – X</p> <p>Notetaker - X.</p>	
50 min	<p>BOG2: trend indications</p> <p>Provide trend indication for selected set of model input variables and other relevant parameters (--- to +++ for changes between 2023 and 2050), alongside a “why” explanation on the trend decision (1-2 sentences). (take into account 5 min needed to walk to BOGs)</p> <p><u>Steps to be elaborated upon.</u></p>	Empty table with all parameters.	Prepare table with all parameters for each group – X.	Parameter set to be selected with WP4, WP5 (including WP5.7), WP6, WP7. Important to include: land use change classes (urban, agriculture, forest), population, GDP, other economic indicators. Note that there is also space to think about trend indications for variables beyond the models (e.g. capitals).
5 min	Break (or energizer)		Prepare and lead energizer – X	
50 min	<p>World café: Current climate change strategies</p> <p>World café: Participants represent strategies and interview SSP groups to learn how (or if) they would work in the different SSP worlds.</p> <p>1. Introduction to activity and group division. (5 min) 2. Participants prepare their roles (5 min) (in parallel – SSPs and strategies) 3. World café (20 min) 4. Harvest (20 min)</p>	<p>1. Proposed strategies to discuss.</p> <p>2. Preparation material (inspiration sheet for SSP representatives and interview guide for strategy representatives)</p> <p>Post its with strategies to choose from.</p>	<p>1. Survey analysis: categorization of strategies.– Uni Graz/WUR/UK CEH</p> <p>1. Main facilitator</p> <p>2. Develop preparation materials – WUR/UK CEH/Uni Graz</p> <p>Prepare post its with strategies</p>	<p>In-depth process document for this BOG will be provided in collaboration with WP6.</p> <p>Need to figure out how to work with the main room space for this, how to set it up. This set up would need to be done during the break.</p>

			<p>based on survey analysis - X</p> <p>Co-facilitators support SSP groups; Main facilitator supports strategies</p> <p>3. Notetakers: SSP1- X SSP3- X SSP4- X SSP5- X</p> <p>4. Main facilitator – X Notetaker – X (HUAS students) Observer – X (HUAS students)</p>	
15 min	<p>Next steps and closing statements</p> <p>1. Short wrap-up and overall thanks to stakeholders; Overview of next steps, output (5 min)</p> <p>2. Hand-out of feedback survey (or online link) → not to be completed during session because of time.</p> <p>3. Final discussion/questions (10 min)</p>	Beamer and slides	<p>1. Wrap-up presentation – X</p> <p>2. Develop feedback survey – X Hand out survey (or link??) - X</p> <p>4. Facilitator – X Notetaker – X</p>	<p>Make sure that the end time is kept. Check beforehand if people need to leave early.</p> <p>Feedback survey- not sure if this is also together with the monitoring WP?</p>
	Closure			
Right after workshop closure.	Collecting all material. Make sure photos are taken of all flip-charts. Cleaning up venue	-	Take photos – X	Original material needs to be stored somewhere for possible check.

Annex 2. Facilitation guides for break out groups in workshop

Facilitation guide for break out group 1: developing SSPs

BOG1: Developing SSP narratives (live workshop) – guide for co-facilitators

Guiding script and questions are provided in this document for **co-facilitators** of each group, as well as what outputs are expected. There are also some specific tasks highlighted in this document for **notetakers** and for **visualizers** (combined role). For each SSP group, there will be one co-facilitator, one note-taker, and one visualizer (at times combined with previous role). We encourage you to go through this document together to make sure you know exactly who is doing what when and what you can expect from each other.

Time	Activity	Guiding comments/questions	Outputs	Notes
Pre-workshop	Setup	<p>Live workshop, for each SSP group required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Correct number of chairs + table (ideally) - One pager for each group placed on the chairs - Co-facilitators have a plan for how to audio-record the discussion (e.g. via laptop or phone) - Flipchart with key SSP elements on first page and revised list of main factors (from plenary discussion) - Marker for co-facilitators - Post its and pens for participants - Laptop for notetaker – for note taking and for visualization. <p>Group division will happen before this BOG. Preparation for this will happen before workshop.</p>		
2-5 min	Introduction to scenario development activity	Welcome to SSP#. We are now in a world of (list key elements from one pager/info sheets). You have received one pager for this SSP, which you will	1 volunteer to present the narrative.	

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		<p>have the chance to read to familiarize yourselves further with the world you are now inhabiting.</p> <p>Before we start, a few reminders:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) You are at liberty to develop their own stories. The 1 pager is intended as a guide, but you are free to develop your own stories based on your local knowledge and the case study context (which may be different to the context at a higher scale). 2) Remember that we have invited you for a reason- the point is for you to bring in your point of view. For example, if you have expertise regarding a specific sector, share this perspective. 3) In this process, we will be using AI to as a tool to enhance creative thinking. The visuals we produce are not meant to be “perfect” or “final”, rather, they are meant to support the process. Just like with the narratives, stakeholders will be given the chance to provide comments following workshop as well. <p>We will need a volunteer to present the SSP you come up with later today. This is short and informal- just 5 minutes, and meant to stimulate discussion, questions, and comments</p>		
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		from the wider group so that everyone becomes familiar with all scenarios developed. Who will volunteer from this group?		
5 min	Participants read 1 page scenario description			
5 min	Participants have the chance to ask clarification questions.	As a reminder, the point of the scenarios in this project is to support the development of robust strategies. They are not meant to be predictive. It is not about the likelihood of this scenario happening; rather, it is about what we would do <i>if</i> this world happened. That being said, it is important that you can all put yourself in this scenario world and can accept the fundamental assumptions of this world. Are you all able to do that? Does anyone have any clarification questions?	All participants are happy to be in this SSP group.	Crucial that all participants are happy in this group. The process will be jeopardized if there is one participants who cannot accept the key assumptions of the SSP world they are in.
~25 min	Creative development of scenarios: Identification main developments between 2023 and 2050	<p><u>(The world) 2050 situation of case study area in SSP world</u></p> <p>[Note to co-facilitators: Participants must first agree on the general developments that happen in this SSP world for the case study. This is needed before proceeding to the scenario development process. Therefore, facilitate discussion around the following questions.]</p> <p>What is the main idea of what the [case study area] will look like in 2050?</p> <p>Guiding questions: 1) What does the [case study area] look like in 2050?</p>	<p>Co-facilitators: Around 3-5 post its (from the group, in all cases) on timeline at 2050 with main ideas and values of the future case study area.</p> <p>Agreement about the main idea of the case study area in 2050, in synthesis post-it(s).</p> <p>Visualizers: One (preliminary) visualization of the [case study area] in 2050.</p> <p>Notetakers: carefully capture discussion and main ideas.</p>	Post-it color = A

		<p>2) It is the year 2050. You wake up on a regular morning. What do you see looking out of your window? What do you hear? How do you feel?</p> <p>3) What values guide this world? What do people find important?</p> <p>AI: For visualizers: First visualization of 2050 world: view out of the window. If there is disagreement, visualization of the conflicting ideas of the 2050 world.</p> <p>For co-facilitators: Guiding questions about visualization: 4) Is this how you (broadly) imagine the [case study area] in 2050? 5) If disagreement: What elements are most important in the different visualizations of the 2050 [case study area]? (What can we agree on? If conflicting, what is behind these ideas that is important to keep?)</p> <p>Once agreement has been reached over the broad outline of what the case study are will look like in this SSP world in 2050, start the scenario development process.</p>		
~40 min		<p><u>(The plot) Evolution of main drivers</u> Guiding questions: 1) What are the most important</p>	<p>Co-facilitators: 1) At least 12 post its (~3-4 per participant) for main developments</p>	<p>Remind stakeholders to look at list of main drivers discussed</p>

		<p>developments that have led to this world?</p> <p>2) What are the main events between 2023 and 2050 that would happen based on these developments?</p> <p>[Note to co-facilitators: Allow for creative process to happen before, if needed, moving on with the following guiding questions].</p> <p>3) What would those developments mean for [SECTORS/THEMES] ? → especially invite participants that are experts in specific sectors (e.g. agriculture, energy transitions)</p> <p>4) How might each main driver evolve over time (until 2050) in this SSP in the case study area?</p> <p>If you were to project yourself- or a different character- into this future (this could be used if participants enjoyed the “look out your window” exercise in the previous session; can remind participants of this if needed):</p> <p>5) How would you experience these developments? Main events? How would you navigate these?</p> <p>6) How would the social and economic conditions affect your wellbeing?</p>	<p>along timeline from 2023 to 2050.</p> <p>2) 3 newspaper headlines for main events (2030, 2040, 2050).</p> <p>3) If relevant: About 3 post its for each [SECTOR/THEME] along timeline, including 1 in 2050, highlighting key developments and impacts on [SECTOR/THEME]</p> <p>Visualizers:</p> <p>1) One iterated visualization of [the case study area] in 2050 based on main developments.</p> <p>2) At least one visualization of a main event to go with a newspaper headline.</p> <p>3) Flip chart with first thoughts about the visualizations, noting down all remarks about the visualization. 5 minutes for this.</p> <p>Notetakers: carefully capture discussion and main developments, events, drivers, and responses to visuals.</p>	<p>previously. Which are most important for this SSP?</p> <p>Reminder: We are using AI as a tool to support creative thinking (i.e. visual does not have to be perfect at this stage, it is meant to support the process).</p> <p>Post it colors: B = developments C = events D = Visualization related</p>
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		<p>Visualization: For visualizers: Visualization of [case study area] in 2050 based on the developments discussed.</p> <p>For co-facilitators: Guiding questions for visualization: 1) Is this how you imagined it? 2) What is missing? What would you change? Add? (if there is disagreement just document this, we just want impressions)</p> <p>[Iterate visual to incorporate changes of 2050 end point]</p> <p>[Note to co-facilitators and visualizers: the visualization process is time and stakeholder dependent, and it may be possible to do more than one visualization if wanting to focus on e.g. a specific development, or a specific aspect of the case study area].</p> <p>3) Looking at this visual, any other thoughts on overall developments?</p> <p>For development of newspaper headlines: Visualization of at least one main event to support development of newspaper headlines. Can also visualize newspaper headlines as a command.</p>		
20 min	Creative development of scenarios: Develop the narrative	The purpose of this session is supposed to form the basis of the storyline that will allow for the narratives to be	Co-facilitators: Some arrows connecting events and developments.	

		<p>developed at a later stage. It is therefore about bringing the separate elements you have come up with so far, all together.</p> <p>Guiding questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) How are the events connected? 2) What are key moments in time? (e.g. as a result of how main developments connect) 3) What are the underlying values of this [case study area] in this scenario world? 4) What are the main drivers behind change? 	<p>Flipchart with bullet points.</p> <p>Notetakers: carefully capture discussion and main ideas.</p>	
5 min	Add title	<p>What is the title of your scenario narrative?</p> <p>Confirm who will present (can be through nominations or voting).</p>	1 title for the developed scenario.	

BOG1: Developing SSP narratives (online workshops) – guide for co-facilitators

Guiding script and questions are provided in this document for **co-facilitators** of each group, as well as what outputs are expected. There are also some specific tasks highlighted in this document for **notetakers**. For each SSP group, there will be one co-facilitator and one notetaker- we encourage you to go through this document together to make sure you know exactly who is doing what when and what you can expect from each other.

Time	Activity	Guiding comments/questions	Outputs	Notes
Pre-workshop	Setup virtual board	<p>Online workshop, virtual board requires (based on this process document):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spaces for ready text (key SSP elements and revised list of main factors from plenary discussion) - Three different main “spaces” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Space for writing 	Virtual board ready for participants to use.	This is probably clearer if the remainder of this process is read!

		<p>text to capture key ideas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Space for participants to add post its notes <p>- One of these main spaces needs a “timeline” structure above (2020, 2030, 2040, 2050), and space for post its to go below.</p>		
2-5 min	Introduction to scenario development activity	<p>Welcome to SSP#. We are now in a world of (list key elements from one pager/info sheets). You have received one pagers for this SSP, which you will have the chance to read to familiarize yourselves further with the world you are now inhabiting.</p> <p>Before we start, a few reminders:</p> <p>4) You are at liberty to develop their own stories. The 1 pager is intended as a guide, but you are free to develop your own stories based on your local knowledge and the case study context (which may be different to the context at a higher scale).</p> <p>5) Remember that we have invited you for a reason- the point is for you to bring in your point of view. For example, if you have expertise regarding a specific sector, share this perspective.</p>	1 volunteer to present the narrative.	

		<p>6) In this process, we will be using AI to as a tool to enhance creative thinking. The visuals we produce are not meant to be “perfect” or “final”, rather, they are meant to support the process. Just like with the narratives, stakeholders will be given the chance to provide comments following workshop as well.</p> <p>We will need a volunteer to present the SSP you come up with later today. This is short and informal- just 5 minutes, and meant to stimulate discussion, questions, and comments from the wider group so that everyone becomes familiar with all scenarios developed. Who will volunteer from this group?</p>		
5 min	Participants read 1 page scenario description	<p>Notetakers should send link with one pagers MS Teams chat. Plan B: if link doesn't work, notetaker should be ready to project on the screen.</p>		
5 min	Participants have the chance to ask clarification questions.	<p>As a reminder, the point of the scenarios in this project is to support the development of robust strategies. They are not meant to be predictive. It is not about the likelihood of this scenario happening; rather, it is about what we would do <i>if</i> this world happened. That being said, it is important that you can all put yourself in this scenario world and can accept the fundamental assumptions of this world. Are you all able to do that?</p>	All participants are happy to be in this SSP group.	

		<p>Does anyone have any clarification questions?</p>		
<p>~20 min</p>	<p>Creative development of scenarios: Identification main developments between 2023 and 2050</p>	<p><u>(The world) 2050 situation of case study area in SSP world</u> [Note to co-facilitators: Participants must first agree on the general developments that happen in this SSP world for the case study. This is needed before proceeding to the scenario development process. Therefore, facilitate discussion around the following questions.]</p> <p>What is the main idea of what the [case study area] will look like in 2050?</p> <p>Process: ~3 post its for participant ideas written down by notetakers based on the ideas they share. Short phrases/keywords on post its.</p> <p>Guiding questions: 6) What does the [case study area] look like in 2050? 7) It is the year 2050. You wake up on a regular morning. What do you see looking out of your window? What do you hear? How do you feel? 8) What values guide this world? What do people find important?</p> <p>If there is disagreement: What elements are most important in the different main ideas of the 2050 [case study area]? (What can we agree on? If conflicting, what is behind these ideas that is important to keep?)</p>	<p>Around 3-5 post its (from the group, in all cases) on timeline at 2050 with main ideas and values of the future case study area.</p> <p>Agreement about the main idea of the case study area in 2050, in synthesis post-it(s). (Notetakers write down synthesis dictated by co-facilitators)</p>	<p>Post-it color = A</p>

		<p>[Note to co-facilitators: Once agreement has been reached over the broad outline of what the case study are will look like in this SSP world in 2050, start the scenario development process.]</p>		
<p>~25 min</p>		<p><u>(The plot) Evolution of main drivers</u> Guiding questions: 7) What are the most important developments that have led to this world? 8) What are the main events between 2023 and 2050 that would happen based on these developments?</p> <p>[Note to co-facilitators: Allow for creative process to happen before, if needed, moving on with the following guiding questions]. 9) What would those developments mean for [SECTORS/THEMES]? → especially invite participants that are experts in specific sectors (e.g. agriculture, energy transitions) 10) How might each main driver evolve over time (until 2050) in this SSP in the case study area?</p> <p>If you were to project yourself- or a different character- into this future (this could be used if participants enjoyed the “look out your window” exercise in the previous session; can remind participants of this if needed):</p>	<p>4) At least 12 post its (~3-4 per participant) for main developments along timeline from 2023 to 2050. 5) 3 newspaper headlines for main events (2030, 2040, 2050). 6) If relevant: About 3 post its for each [SECTOR/THEME] along timeline, including 1 in 2050, highlighting key developments and impacts on [SECTOR/THEME].</p>	<p>Remind stakeholders to look at list of main drivers discussed previously. Which are most important for this SSP?</p> <p>Post it color = B (developments)) C (events)</p>

		<p>11) How would you experience these developments? Main events? How would you navigate these?</p> <p>12) How would the social and economic conditions affect your wellbeing?</p>		
~15 min	Creative development of scenarios: Develop the narrative	<p>The purpose of this session is supposed to form the basis of the storyline that will allow for the narratives to be developed at a later stage. It is therefore about bringing the separate elements together.</p> <p>Guiding questions:</p> <p>5) How are the events connected?</p> <p>6) What are key moments in time? (e.g. as a result of how main developments connect)</p> <p>7) What are the underlying values of this [case study area] in this scenario world?</p> <p>8) What are the main drivers behind change?</p>	<p>Some arrows connecting events and developments.</p> <p>Online chart with bullet points.</p>	
5 min	Add title	<p>What is the title of your scenario narrative?</p> <p>Confirm who will present (can be through nominations or voting)- can be in pair if they feel more comfortable.</p>	1 title for the developed scenario.	Need to send final outputs of boards to stakeholders (especially for those presenting).

Facilitation guide for break out group 2: trend indications

BOG2 – Trend indications for future changes in model parameters and other scenario characteristics

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Goal: Provide trend indication for selected set of model input variables and other relevant scenario characteristics

Duration: approximately 45 minutes

Overall process: groups with the same composition as during BOG1, where they developed one SSP. These groups now build on the results from BOG1 and for “their own” SSP, complete a table with around 10 model parameters and other scenario characteristics. The two main questions to be answered are:

1. What is the trend until 2050 for the parameter? (trend from -5 to +5)
2. What is the logic behind the change in the SSP? (2-3 sentences that explain why the change is as indicated).

Detailed (content) instructions for stakeholders:

Groups should provide a trend indication EITHER for two separate time periods (2023-2030 and 2031-2050) when developments are nonlinear or for one time period (2023-2050) when developments are linear. An explanation of the trends in words in 2-3 sentences for each characteristic can be anything that is useful given the narrative that the group developed in BOG1. The material developed in BOG1 should be accessible for stakeholders to check what was decided in BOG1.

Trend indications should be on a scale from -5 to +5 (very low-low-medium-strong-very strong increase/decrease) of average change in the specified period. For the sectors (water, energy, and food), an order of priority needs to be indicated (see Table 1).

The question related to Energy is slightly more elaborate and relates to five sectors with one priority (see below). Explanation might need to be slightly longer, but should not treat all five sectors separately.

List of model parameters and other characteristics

Element	What
Total population	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
GDP growth	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Environmental behaviour	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Water	Prioritise list of water sectors. In case of water stress, which sector will be prioritised?
Energy	Prioritise list of energy sources. What is main source of energy?
Food	Prioritise farming practices. Conventional or organic?
Agricultural area	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Social capital	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Manufactured capital	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5
Human capital	Trend of rate of change -5 to +5

Detailed explanation of model parameters or proxies

(Note for facilitators: Read these descriptions carefully, but use this only when stakeholders are in doubt what is meant; this will likely refer to environmental behaviour and the three capitals)

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Total population:

Ask stakeholders for the trend in **total population** on a scale from +5 to -5 in a given time period.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP):

This is a measure for economic development. Ask stakeholders for the trend in **yearly average GDP growth** in a given time period.

Environmental behaviour:

This is an **index for overall environmental behaviour**. An increase, in general, relates to an increase in pro-nature attitude for any type of actor. This could relate to development of green technology; dietary preferences towards vegetarianism; direct nature protection measures; mobility; heating systems etc. It depends on the scenario that was developed, what actor group(s) should be specified (e.g., NGOs, citizens, policy makers, businesses) and what the increase/decrease refers to specifically. The accompanying text should explain this.

Water:

Given a certain water supply, what will be the order of priority when choices have to be made for satisfying water demand. In which order will the water demand be satisfied? For a given time period, four sectors should be ordered from first priority (1) to last priority (4). The four sectors are: agriculture, domestic, industry, and nature.

Agriculture:

This aspect relates to food production. Will organic food production be prioritised, or conventional farming systems? For a given time period, two production systems should be ordered as first (1) or second (2) priority.

Energy:

This aspect relates to energy consumption. Which type of energy will be prioritised in the main energy using sectors (industry, residential, commercial, agricultural and transportation)? For a given time period, provide the most important source of energy for each of the five sectors. Included are three types of energy: electricity, natural gas, fossil fuels; and five sectors: industry, residential, commercial, agricultural and transportation.

Agricultural area:

This aspect relates to the change in **total area used for production of agricultural products**. This includes arable land (crops) and grassland (for grazing). A main element to consider here is the choice to either produce all food locally or to focus on food import. Important to invite stakeholders to include this in their description.

Detailed explanation of 'capitals'

We are also interested in quantifying the stocks of resources that people have available to adapt and cope with the challenges of climate change within the scenarios in addition to financial resources. These include stocks of human, social and manufactured capital detailed below. For the same climate impact, people with lower levels of each of these

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capitals are more likely to be more vulnerable than those with higher levels of capital. All three are more general indices, that are defined as:

Social capital: index covering all aspects that relate to structures, institutions, **networks**, and relationships. It includes families, communities, businesses, voluntary organisations, and the political system.

Manufactured capital: index covering all aspects that relate to the entire **physical man-made stock**, including infrastructure (roads, canals), buildings, but also machinery, cars, etc.

Human capital: index covering all aspects that relate to the **individual** knowledge, skills, and health that people invest in and accumulate. It includes education, training, intelligence, skills, health, etc., but also often assumes physical entities such as hospital, health care system, universities etc.

For all three, changes could relate to many different aspects of the scenario. an indication of the overall trend should be provided; the accompanying text should explain what the decrease/increase specifically refers to, using the examples provided in the descriptions above.

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Facilitation guide for break out group 3: climate change strategies

BOG3: Climate strategies & SSPs - World Café (AKA Speed Dating for SSPs) – (Live workshop) guide for facilitators

Guiding script and questions are provided in this document for **main facilitators** and **co-facilitators** of each group, as well as what outputs are expected. There are also some specific tasks highlighted in this document for **notetakers**.

Time	Activity	Guiding comments/questions	Outputs	Notes
During break	Setup	<p>Preparation includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preliminary idea on possible participants that could represent strategies from each SSP group is needed, based on participant list, group division, and survey responses. – SC, WUR, & CCS <p>Break comes right before this, so during that time need to set up room in a way that makes this work.</p> <p>For live workshop, this means at minimum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Correct number of chairs in circle + table per SSP group + team (see note below) - SSP inspiration guides for each group placed on the chairs (if possible, also with a 'sign' near the group indicating which SSP it is) - Flipchart with climate strategies on sticky notes ready for participants - Interview guides for climate strategies in a pile next to the flipchart - A bell or other noise maker to facilitate the 'switch' - Stack of individual reflection sheets ready to be passed around quickly for the 'harvest' at the end - Notetakers responsible for moving trends table and key takeaways material to SSP table (e.g. the relevant flipcharts), so that SSP group has this at hand to refer to. 		<p>Material:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of climate strategies per case study - SSP inspiration guides - Interview guides - Reflection sheets

		<p>[Note to (co)-facilitators: There should be at least 1 group for each SSP that was addressed in prior breakout groups in the workshops. The exact figuring out of the number of breakout groups/strategies needs to happen before for each case study. Make plan a few days before, and adjust based on morning (live)/first day (online) attendance.]</p>		
<p>5 min</p>	<p>Quick introduction to activity (more instructions will come in groups)</p>	<p>****<i>When people enter the room, direct them to sit in the chairs near the SSP they are most familiar with after the previous activities during the workshop.</i></p> <p>Main facilitator: This final activity is meant to be a fun way to get you both experiencing your SSP worlds that you have created (this morning/yesterday), and learning about how they may affect existing climate strategies in [CASE].</p> <p>This activity will be energetic and interactive, and it may be a bit frantic as we try to squeeze a lot in a short amount of time! So please, bear with us and trust us as we move you through the exercise.</p> <p>In this activity, some of you will take on the role of the SSP of your table. You ARE the SSP. Others will take on the role of a specific climate adaptation or mitigation strategy that you are already familiar with.</p> <p>We are going to follow a world café structure, where those representing the climate strategies will interview an SSP group to find out how this strategy would fare in each future world defined by the SSP. We provide a list of questions, such as “am I (the climate strategy) still feasible in this SSP? Will this SSP provide an enabling governance context? Etc.”. Those of you who are embodying an SSP will use your knowledge of the</p>		

		<p>SSP that you have gathered over the past few hours of the workshop to respond to the person interviewing you with how you, the SSP, will impact them. We have provided some materials to remind you of key characteristics of your SSP. After you have interviewed for a specific amount of time, we will [ring a bell?] and the climate strategies will rotate to the next SSP. We will continue [X] times, after which we will harvest the insights that come up during the exercise.</p> <p>You will have a bit of time to prepare, and during that time you will also receive all the guidance documents for each role. Once we are all ready there will be further instructions.</p>		
2 min	Group division	<p>Choose 1 people from your SSP group to become climate strategies, and the rest to stay and embody your SSP. [Depending on number of participants, if high number of participants, might have 2 people per SSP group become different strategies. To be determined before workshop].</p> <p>Those of you who are SSPs: stay at the table and review the materials we have provided. Remember, you need to be prepared to respond to the climate strategies about how you will impact them. You will have a co-facilitator there to help you.</p> <p>Those of you who are climate strategies, come over to this flipchart and select a climate adaptation/mitigation strategy that you are already familiar with. You are now embodying this strategy! Please take an interview guide and a pen with you.</p>		The exact figuring out of the number of breakout groups/strategies needs to happen before for each case study. Make plan a few days before, and adjust based on morning (live)/first day (online) attendance.
5 min	Preparation (in parallel)	<p>In parallel: <u>SSP tasks (1 co-facilitator per SSP group):</u> 1) Co-facilitators make sure SSP embodiments are at their respective tables.</p>	For climate strategies: main facilitator ensures participants select a	Each SSP table should have: 1) SSP representatives 2) Co-facilitator (of that SSP)

		<p>2) Co-facilitator helps participants review their inspiration sheet. If needed, remind participants of key learnings of the day (list of factors, key drivers and main events identified, and trend indications).</p> <p>3) Co-facilitator prompts participants to make a plan of action. What kind of role do they want to play? What part(s) of their SSP do they want to embody?</p> <p>4) Remind participants to jot down any quick thoughts throughout the process, but they will have more in-depth reflection time at the end.</p> <p><u>Climate strategies tasks (main facilitator)</u></p> <p>5) Main facilitator helps ‘climate strategy’ participants choose the strategy they will embody. Ensure there are selections from the different types of climate strategies if you can.</p> <p>6) Give each climate strategy an interview guide and ensure they have a pen.</p> <p>7) Remind participants to jot down any quick thoughts throughout the process, but they will have more in-depth reflection time at the end.</p> <p>8) Answer any questions about the activity.</p>	<p>strategy; ensure representation of strategy types.</p>	<p>3) Notetaker</p>
<p>20 min</p>	<p>World café: Strategies interview the SSPs</p>	<p>Okay, so climate strategies, find an SSP to start with! You should have maximum 2 strategies interviewing any SSP at once, so try to distribute yourselves. Jot down any key insights that come out of your interviews.</p> <p>When we [ring a bell?] you will rotate to the next SSP! We will give a 1 minute warning before rotating. If you have any questions please ask your co-facilitator! We will do [X] rounds.</p> <p><i>Note to co-facilitators:</i></p>	<p>Strategies record key learnings on interview guide.</p> <p>(Notetakers capture conversations as much as possible).</p>	<p>Note takers: Pay careful attention and record as much of the conversation as possible.</p>

		<p>After 1 minute warning, remind participants to jot down any quick thoughts.</p> <p>Note to main facilitator: Time per SSP interview depends on number of SSP groups. Ideally the following, but adjust accordingly if the explanation takes too long.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If 4 SSP groups – 5 min per group. - If 3 SSP groups - 6 min per group. - If 2 SSP groups – 10 min per group (if moving in pairs to pairs) or 5 min per group (if moving individually). 		
18 min	Harvest: key learnings and close	<p>Ask participants to stop where they are and find a seat!</p> <p>[Co-facilitators quickly hand out the individual reflection sheets!]</p> <p>Individual reflection (5 mins)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We are going to take a few minutes for you to jot down the key insights from your time interviewing the SSPs. We have provided an individual reflection sheet to facilitate that. After five minutes we will come back to the group and ask a few of you to share. <p>Group reflection (10 mins) – main facilitator facilitates</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prompt for the people who were embodying climate strategies. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o How does your strategy fare under some of the SSPs? o Did you have any broader reflections or learnings from the experience embodying this strategy? - Prompt for the people who were embodying SSPs 	Individual reflection sheets filled out and collected at the end.	Reflections from group discussion (captured by notetakers).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How did your SSP impact the climate strategies? ○ Did you have any broader reflections or learnings from the experience embodying this SSP? <p>Close (3 mins)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thank you all so much for jumping into this exercise! We understand this was a challenging task – it can be difficult to imagine these future worlds defined by the SSPs, let alone to understand how our existing climate strategies might fit into them. - This session was a quick and frantic and snapshot of the type of questions we will try to answer with our analysis and future workshops to come. If you are confident in your existing strategies, great! If not, if some of your climate strategies didn't fare very well under different SSPs, or may need to be adapted, we are going to be embarking on a more systematic process for generating new strategies and making them more robust to all of these future uncertainties. - Don't forget to hand all your materials back to our co-facilitators who will be going around the room now. - We hope you enjoyed yourselves, and thanks again! Now, we are moving to our more official close. Thanks a lot! 		
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BOG3: Climate strategies & SSPs – World Café (AKA Speed Dating for SSPs) – (Online workshop) guide for facilitators

Guiding script and questions are provided in this document for **main facilitators** and **co-facilitators** of each group, as well as what outputs are expected. There are also some specific tasks highlighted in this document for **notetakers**.

Time	Activity	Guiding comments/questions	Outputs	Notes
During break	Setup	<p>Preparation includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preliminary idea on possible participants that could represent strategies from each SSP group is needed, based on participant list, group division, and survey responses. – SC, WUR, & CCS <p>Break comes right before this, so during that time need to set up room in a way that makes this work.</p> <p>For online workshop, this means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SC will relocate the strategies people. - Notetakers responsible for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Copying and pasting the finalized trends table from BOG2 in the correct part of the BOG3 virtual board (indicated on board) o Copying and pasting the key developments, drivers and final takeaways from BOG1 into the correct part of the BOG3 virtual board (indicated on board). <p>[Note to (co)-facilitators: There should be at least 1 group for each SSP that was addressed in prior breakout groups in the workshops. The exact figuring out of the number of breakout groups/strategies needs to happen before for each case study. Make plan a few days before, and adjust based on morning (live)/first day (online) attendance.]</p>		<p>Material:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of climate strategies per case study - SSP inspiration guides - Interview guides - Reflection sheets
5 min	Quick introduction to activity (more instructions)	<p>Main facilitator:</p> <p>This final activity is meant to be a fun way to get you both experiencing your SSP worlds that you have created (this morning/yesterday), and</p>		

	will come in groups)	<p>learning about how they may affect existing climate strategies in [CASE].</p> <p>This activity will be energetic and interactive, and it may be a bit frantic as we try to squeeze a lot in a short amount of time! So please, bear with us and trust us as we move you through the exercise.</p> <p>In this activity, some of you will take on the role of the SSP of your table. You ARE the SSP. Others will take on the role of a specific climate adaptation or mitigation strategy that you are already familiar with.</p> <p>We are going to follow a world café structure, where those representing the climate strategies will interview an SSP group to find out how this strategy would fare in each future world defined by the SSP. We provide a list of questions, such as “am I (the climate strategy) still feasible in this SSP? Will this SSP provide an enabling governance context? Etc.”. Those of you who are embodying an SSP will use your knowledge of the SSP that you have gathered over the past few hours of the workshop to respond to the person interviewing you with how you, the SSP, will impact them. We have provided some materials to remind you of key characteristics of your SSP. After you have interviewed for a specific amount of time, we will [ring a bell?] and the climate strategies will rotate to the next SSP. We will continue [X] times, after which we will harvest the insights that come up during the exercise.</p> <p>You will have a bit of time to prepare, and during that time you will also receive all the guidance documents for each role. Once we are all ready there will be further instructions.</p>		
2 min	Group division	Choose 1 people from your SSP group to become climate strategies, and the rest to stay and embody your SSP. [Depending on number of		The exact figuring out of the number of breakout groups/strategies

		<p>participants, if high number of participants, might have 2 people per SSP group become different strategies. To be determined before workshop].</p> <p>Those of you who are SSPs: stay at the table and review the materials we have provided. Remember, you need to be prepared to respond to the climate strategies about how you will impact them. You will have a co-facilitator there to help you.</p> <p>Those of you who are climate strategies, come over to this flipchart and select a climate adaptation/mitigation strategy that you are already familiar with. You are now embodying this strategy! Please take an interview guide and a pen with you.</p>		<p>needs to happen before for each case study. Make plan a few days before, and adjust based on morning (live)/first day (online) attendance.</p>
5 min	Preparation (in parallel)	<p>In parallel: <u>SSP tasks (1 co-facilitator per SSP group):</u> 9) Co-facilitators make sure SSP embodiments are at their respective tables. 10) Co-facilitator helps participants review their inspiration sheet. If needed, remind participants of key learnings of the day (list of factors, key drivers and main events identified, and trend indications). 11) Co-facilitator prompts participants to make a plan of action. What kind of role do they want to play? What part(s) of their SSP do they want to embody? 12) Remind participants to jot down any quick thoughts throughout the process, but they will have more in-depth reflection time at the end.</p> <p><u>Climate strategies tasks (main facilitator)</u> 13) Main facilitator helps 'climate strategy' participants choose the strategy they will embody.</p>	<p>For climate strategies: main facilitator ensures participants select a strategy; ensure representation of strategy types.</p>	<p>Each SSP table should have: 1) SSP representatives 2) Co-facilitator (of that SSP) 3) Notetaker</p>

		<p>Ensure there are selections from the different types of climate strategies if you can.</p> <p>14) Give each climate strategy an interview guide and ensure they have a pen.</p> <p>15) Remind participants to jot down any quick thoughts throughout the process, but they will have more in-depth reflection time at the end.</p> <p>16) Answer any questions about the activity.</p>		
20 min	World café: Strategies interview the SSPs	<p>Okay, so climate strategies, find an SSP to start with! You should have maximum 2 strategies interviewing any SSP at once, so try to distribute yourselves. Jot down any key insights that come out of your interviews.</p> <p>When we [ring a bell?] you will rotate to the next SSP! We will give a 1 minute warning before rotating. If you have any questions please ask your co-facilitator! We will do [X] rounds.</p> <p><i>Note to co-facilitators:</i> After 1 minute warning, remind participants to jot down any quick thoughts.</p> <p><i>Note to main facilitator:</i> Time per SSP interview depends on number of SSP groups. Ideally the following, but adjust accordingly if the explanation takes too long.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If 4 SSP groups – 5 min per group. - If 3 SSP groups - 6 min per group. - If 2 SSP groups – 10 min per group (if moving in pairs to pairs) or 5 min per group (if moving individually). 	<p>Strategies record key learnings on interview guide.</p> <p>(Notetakers capture conversations as much as possible).</p>	Note takers: Pay careful attention and record as much of the conversation as possible.
18 min	Harvest: key learnings and close	<p>Ask participants to stop where they are and find a seat!</p> <p><i>[Co-facilitators quickly hand out the individual reflection sheets!]</i></p> <p>Individual reflection (5 mins)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We are going to take a few minutes for you to jot down 	<p>Individual reflection sheets filled out and collected at the end.</p> <p>Reflections from group</p>	

		<p>the key insights from your time interviewing the SSPs. We have provided an individual reflection sheet to facilitate that. After five minutes we will come back to the group and ask a few of you to share.</p> <p>Group reflection (10 mins) – main facilitator facilitates</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prompt for the people who were embodying climate strategies. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o How does your strategy fare under some of the SSPs? o Did you have any broader reflections or learnings from the experience embodying this strategy? - Prompt for the people who were embodying SSPs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o How did your SSP impact the climate strategies? o Did you have any broader reflections or learnings from the experience embodying this SSP? <p>Close (3 mins)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thank you all so much for jumping into this exercise! We understand this was a challenging task – it can be difficult to imagine these future worlds defined by the SSPs, let alone to understand how our existing climate strategies might fit into them. - This session was a quick and frantic and snapshot of the type of questions we will try to answer with our analysis and future workshops to come. If you are confident in your existing strategies, great! If not, if some of your 	<p>discussion (captured by notetakers).</p>	
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		<p>climate strategies didn't fare very well under different SSPs, or may need to be adapted, we are going to be embarking on a more systematic process for generating new strategies and making them more robust to all of these future uncertainties.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Don't forget to hand all your materials back to our co-facilitators who will be going around the room now.- We hope you enjoyed yourselves, and thanks again! Now, we are moving to our more official close. Thanks a lot!		
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